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**Cepheid X-ray Emission based on
eRASS1 Catalogue**

A.A. Matrokhin,¹ M.E. Sachkov,¹ and D.A. Kovaleva¹

¹*Institute of Astronomy of the Russian Acad. Sci., 48 Pyatnitskaya Str., 109017 Moscow, Russia*

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Abstract

This study investigates the X-ray emission from Cepheid variable stars using data from the eROSITA telescope onboard the SRG mission. Cepheids are crucial "standard candles" due to their well-known period-luminosity relationship. While some Cepheids, like δ Cephei, have shown pulsation-phase-dependent X-ray emission, others, such as Polaris and V473 Lyrae, exhibit X-ray emission independent of pulsation, often attributed to low-mass companions. Previous targeted observations with Chandra and XMM-Newton were limited. The all-sky X-ray survey by eROSITA provides an unprecedented opportunity for a comprehensive study. We cross-matched a combined catalog of 15620 Cepheids from Gaia DR3 and the "Classical Cepheids in Milky Way" catalog with the eRASS1 X-ray catalog. Our analysis yielded 107 potential Cepheid-X-ray source matches. A detailed examination of identification ambiguity using Gaia data reduced the number of robust candidates to 18. We present preliminary results, highlighting 3 highly probable and 12 probable X-ray emitting Cepheids, while 89 cases require further investigation.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Cepheids are variable stars of different types that can be separated into three groups: so called Classical Cepheids (DCEPs according to the GCVS classification), type II Cepheids (T2CEP) and anomalous Cepheids (ACEPs). In this article, we will talk exclusively about the first type of these stars.

DCEPs (their prototype is δ Cep) are fundamental astronomical objects, serving as "standard candles" for measuring cosmic distances due to the established relationship between their pulsation period and intrinsic luminosity. As their pulsational parameters (periods) are connected with main stellar parameters such as mass and effective temperature, these stars can be used as an independent laboratory for stellar evolution model. So, understanding their physical properties, including emission across various electromagnetic spectra, is crucial.

DCEPs are luminous and massive stars ($M \sim 3 - 11M_{\odot}$).

The pulsation cycle in the Cepheid atmosphere can generate a shock wave. This may be one of the possible causes of X-ray bursts, and the most likely if we assume that the source of the X-ray radiation is the Cepheid itself.

X-ray bursts have been discovered in several Cepheids ([1])

The recent appearance of all-sky surveys in the visible and X-ray ranges allows us to hope for the detection of X-rays in a larger number of classical Cepheids.

2. DATA

This study relies on a multi-wavelength approach, integrating data from comprehensive X-ray and optical surveys. The primary X-ray data were sourced from the first eROSITA All-Sky Survey (eRASS1) [2], conducted by the Spektr-RG mission, providing an unprecedented deep and uniform coverage of the celestial sphere in X-rays. For the optical counterparts and accurate stellar parameters of Cepheids, we utilized a combined catalog of these pulsating variables, leveraging the precise astrometric and photometric information from Gaia Data Release 3 (DR3) [3] alongside other established Cepheid catalogs. This combination of high-quality observational data is crucial for robustly identifying and characterizing X-ray emitting Cepheids.

2.1. eROSITA All-Sky Survey (eRASS1) Catalog

The X-ray data utilized in this study were obtained from the first eROSITA all-sky survey (eRASS1) [2]. The eROSITA (extended ROentgen Survey with an Imaging Telescope Array) instrument is the primary instrument aboard the Spektr-RG (SRG) mission, a joint Russian-German X-ray observatory. The first all-sky survey, eRASS1, was completed on June 11, 2020, covering the western galactic hemisphere and resulting in a catalog containing 1.1 million X-ray sources.

2.2. Gaia Cepheids

The Gaia Data Release 3 (GaiaDR3) [3] provided a comprehensive and highly precise catalog of celestial objects, which notably included a dedicated sample of Cepheid variable stars. This catalog comprises 15021 Cepheids of various types, predominantly classical Cepheids. A significant fraction of the Gaia DR3 Cepheids are located in the Magellanic Clouds. 5221 objects are distributed across the broader all-sky region, including stars within the Milky Way field, globular and open clusters within our galaxy.

2.3. Cepheids Catalogs

For this study, a combined list of Cepheids was compiled. This list integrates data from the Gaia DR3 catalog, which includes over 15021 Cepheids (a portion of which are located in our galaxy, with others in the Small and Large Magellanic Clouds), and the "Classical Cepheids in Milky Way" catalog [4]. This merging was necessary because many well-known and bright Cepheids were not included in the Gaia catalog. The resulting combined list contains 15620 stars. Positional errors from Gaia are considered negligibly small.

3. METHODS

To achieve the objectives of this study, we cross-matched our compiled Cepheid catalog with the eROSITA All-Sky Survey (eRASS1) X-ray source catalog.

3.1. Cross-matching

Identification between the compiled Cepheid list and the eRASS1 X-ray source catalog was performed based on coordinates. The identification radius was set to three times the eRASS1 positional error for each source. This procedure yielded 107 potential Cepheid-X-ray source matches.

3.2. Ambiguity

To assess the uniqueness of the identified matches, we utilized the Gaia catalog to check for other objects within the error circles around the X-ray sources. It was found that various error circles contained anywhere from 1 to over 1000 objects from Gaia (an example of a possible situation is shown in Figure 2). To focus on more reliable matches, we limited our selection to cases where no more than 5 other objects, in addition to the Cepheid, fell within the error circle. This refined selection resulted in 18 such candidates.

4. RESULTS

The analysis of the cross-matching results for the 18 refined candidates revealed several categories of matches.

Figure 1. An example of a possible situation, that shows Cepheid-X-Ray source match with circle of error and other objects.

Highly Probable X-ray Cepheids: β Dor, ζ Gem, OGLE LMC-CEP-4494 - only the Cepheid fell within the error circle.

We present the first 18 out of 107 matches in Table 1. Also, these first 18 matches are shown on the sky map in galactic coordinates in Figure 2.

We believe that 3 objects: β Dor, ζ Gem, OGLE LMC-CEP-4494 are the most likely new X-ray Cepheids. There are no other Gaia objects other than Cepheids near these X-ray sources.

We refer the remaining 12 objects (out of the 18 considered, with the exception of the 3 most likely Cepheids - β Dor, ζ Gem, OGLE LMC-CEP-4494, and 3 Cepheids, where X-ray emission's attribution to Cepheids is questionable - OGLE LMC-CEP-4016, CRTS J124606.5-423806, OGLE GD-CEP-1750) to the probable X-ray Cepheids.

5. DISCUSSION

In this study we have found 107 matches in total of X-ray sources and Classical Cepheids. Of 1.1 million X-ray sources of the western galactic hemisphere, 107 had at least one possible

Table 1. First 18 X-Ray - Cepheid matches. IAUNAME – name of X-Ray source in eRASS1, N – number of objects fallen in error circles, Cepheid Name – name of the Cepheid in Simbad, Flux - Source flux in 0.2-2.3 keV band, G - magnitude in G band.

IAUNAME	N	Cepheid Name	Flux, $\cdot 10^{-14} \cdot$ $erg \cdot s^{-1} \cdot cm^{-2}$	G, mag
1eRASS J053337.5-622924	1	bet Dor	26.9	3.59
1eRASS J055217.4-671629	1	OGLE LMC-CEP-4494	1.4	14.85
1eRASS J070406.4+203412	1	zet Gem	8.8	3.54
1eRASS J043832.1-673845	3	OGLE LMC-CEP-16	2.4	14.73
1eRASS J044839.2-642344	2	Gaia DR1 4663192228315671808	1.9	16.17
1eRASS J045029.6-655211	2	OGLE LMC-CEP-3420	1.0	15.52
1eRASS J050605.8-645020	4	OGLE LMC-CEP-3583	1.9	15.46
1eRASS J052724.4-652110	5	OGLE LMC-CEP-4016	1.0	15.26
1eRASS J053009.9-631612	2	OGLE LMC-CEP-4071	0.8	16.76
1eRASS J054753.0-661756	5	OGLE LMC-CEP-4407	0.3	16.65
1eRASS J055058.9-631343	2	OGLE LMC-CEP-4473	0.8	16.06
1eRASS J174825.6-591029	2	TZ Pav	5.0	12.45
1eRASS J014626.5-732840	2	OGLE SMC-CEP-4936	2.0	16.89
1eRASS J060404.9-651920	2	[KDM2001] 7100	0.4	15.91
1eRASS J060550.8-672500	3	OGLE LMC-CEP-4580	0.2	16.88
1eRASS J094531.6+121445	1	CRTS J094531.4+121442	3.6	16.42
1eRASS J124607.3-423818	3	CRTS J124606.5-423806	3.2	14.28
1eRASS J151903.3-561244	5	OGLE GD-CEP-1750	1.9	18.66

Figure 2. Left: The first 18 objects examined in this paper. Right: The area marked with a blue rectangle in the left figure.

match with Classical Cepheid list. We think that all these 107 objects can be considered as possible candidates for X-ray Cepheids. For this study, we were limited a list of objects that are inside a separation circle (a circle with a radius of separation of X-ray source and Cepheid) there are no more than 5 Gaia sources. Data on these 18 objects are summarized in the Table 1.

Observations by other authors have shown that archetypal Cepheid, β Dor, is highly probable X-Ray source [5], and in our study it has confirmed.

R Cru, V659 Cen, S Mus were previously observed in X-rays [5] and fell within the studied region of the sky, but were not detected in eRASS1. Recently it was found that for η Aql Cepheid ([6]) there is a pulsational phase dependance for X-ray flux. The deviation from the maximum flux can be up to 4 times. If eRASS1 observations of these Cepheids were carried out near the phase of the minimum X-ray flux, this may be the reason for their undetection.

We can conclude that the remaining 14 objects (out of 18) are new candidates for X-ray Cepheids.

As the next steps, we plan to consider the second half of the sky as observed by the EROSITA satellite. We will determine the phase of the brightness in the visible range, near which X-ray observations were made, in order to find the dependence of the X-ray flux on the flux in the visible range. In addition, as data on the remaining X-ray surveys are published (we recall that a total of 6 were done, only one was published), it will be possible to model real X-ray light curves.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors of this work declare that they have no conflicts of interest.

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